
Effect of Cooking Temperature on Iron Extraction from Spinach Using Thiocyanate-Based Colorimetric Analysis

Abstract

One of the most popular sources of iron in foods is spinach. Optimal iron extraction conditions from spinach remain unclear. Spinach may be iron rich but a human body is not able to access the maximum iron content present, and that is explained by the presence of oxalates in it. Oxalates are chemically bonded to iron, and are insoluble. However, literature itself contradicts the effect of cooking on iron content; oxalate breakdown increases availability, or the iron ions are leached into the cooking medium. This study investigates how cooking temperature affects iron availability in spinach by measuring Fe^{3+} concentration across five temperatures (40-80°C) using colorimetric analysis of the Fe^{3+} thiocyanate complex. The overall trend between temperature and iron content shows positive correlation ($R=0.948$), with results becoming constant between 60-70°C. The amount of iron content found across the temperature span was 8.12-10.26 mg/100g that is higher than typical literature reported values for spinach iron content, which is associated with acidic conditions. The study does not investigate dietary bioavailability in spinach but rather explores the potential of iron extraction from spinach under laboratory conditions.

Keywords: Spinach, Iron(III), Oxalate, Colorimetry, Thiocyanate complex, Cooking temperature, Iron extraction, Spectrophotometry, Food Chemistry, Thermal Processing

1. Introduction

Spinach is widely known for its high iron content, a vital component in the human diet. Iron forms an essential part of haemoglobin, the oxygen carrier in blood. Although iron requirements vary with gender and age, adults generally need 8-18mg of iron daily (1,2). Cooking temperatures for iron rich foods like spinach have often been debated in many cultures. Some cultures prefer to use spinach raw, whereas others subject it to high levels of heat over a long period, draining it of its vibrant green colour.

Iron (Fe) is a transition metal; it can exist in the states, Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . It can form complex ions. A complex ion has a central metal ion attached to one or more ligands through coordinate covalent bonds. A ligand is a species with a lone pair of electrons, forming a coordinate covalent bond with a transition metal (3). Since iron is a transition element, it forms coloured compounds, such as the red colour in this investigation. In these compounds or complexes, incompletely filled 3d orbitals are split: into higher and lower energy. The energy difference of these split d-orbitals follows the relationship: $\Delta E = hf$. When light falls on the complex, specific wavelengths of the light are absorbed by

an electron which transitions to a higher-energy sublevel. This is called a d-d transition. Therefore, the solution exhibits a colour complementary to the absorbed light.

Figure 1. Diagram showing a d-d transition, in which an electron absorbs energy and moves from a lower-energy to a higher-energy d-orbital sublevel, resulting in the observed colour of the complex (4)

Iron (III) content in foods can be measured by redox titration or by measuring the absorbance of $Fe(SCN)_3$ molecules with a colorimeter. Colorimetry determines concentration of a chemical compound in a solution by measuring spectral absorbance of the compound at a particular wavelength (5). This investigation exploits the ability of iron ions to react with thiocyanate ligand (SCN^-) to form coloured complex ions, in order to detect them. Since Fe^{3+} forms a stable and detectable red complex with potassium thiocyanate, all of the iron ions will be oxidized through the use of nitric acid. SCN^- reacts with Fe^{3+} to form a red-coloured complex:

The detailed reaction involves the treatment of spinach samples with hydrochloric acid and potassium thiocyanate solution:

The reactant, potassium thiocyanate, $KSCN$, is a colourless to white liquid. However, when reacted with iron (III), potassium is displaced and a new product, thiocyanateiron(III), is formed, the solution turns red. The darkness of this colour is dependent on the concentration of iron (III) ions. Red solutions absorb blue light very well, therefore the colorimeter will be set to 470 nm to find the absorbance rate which will be the determination of iron (III) content in spinach (6). The working principle of a colorimeter is based on BeerLambert's law, which states that the absorption of light transmitted through a medium is directly proportional to the concentration of the medium (7).

Spinach contains high levels of oxalates which bind iron to form ferrous oxalate, making iron in spinach unavailable (8). The oxalate ion ($C_2O_4^{2-}$) is a bidentate ligand, meaning that it donates two pairs of electrons to a metal ion to form coordinate covalent bonds. Upon formation of a complex with iron, the ferrous oxalate is found to be poorly soluble (9).

Figure 2. Structure of the oxalate ion ($C_2O_4^{2-}$), a bidentate ligand capable of forming coordinate covalent bonds with a central metal ion at two donor sites (10)

During my primary research, I found mixed opinions regarding cooking iron. Some research would say that cooking reduces iron content (11) because iron ions leach out into the cooking medium. On the other hand, research indicates that the oxalates present in vegetables are inhibited, with soluble oxalate reduction in spinach reaching approximately 67% after boiling (12). High temperatures can break down these complex iron oxalate structures, releasing iron ions (13). This mechanism, observed in aqueous chemical systems, is proposed here to apply analogically to the biological matrix of cooked spinach. When spinach is exposed to higher temperatures, the heat breaks down the bonds between oxalate and iron. It denatures cell membranes and other structures, making iron release more efficient (14).

This study will investigate: how does the changing the cooking temperature [**40°C, 50°C, 60°C, 70°C & 80°C**] of spinach affect its iron content for every 5.00 grams of spinach, determined using colorimetry with the reaction of Fe^{3+} and KSCN? Based on the background information, it can be hypothesized that a positive correlation would be seen between temperature and iron content. High temperatures would break complex structures in spinach and hence, more iron ions would react with KSCN to display a deeper colour, which means a higher absorbance in colorimetry.

2. Methods

2.1 Materials and Apparatus

Table 4

Glassware, equipment, and chemicals used in the investigation, including measurement uncertainties where applicable

Glassware	Equipment	Chemicals & Materials
50 mL Beakers	Water bath (± 0.1)	2 M HCL
Conical flasks	Colorimeter (± 0.001)	Concentrated Nitric acid
Measuring cylinders (± 0.1)	Measuring Balance (± 0.001)	0.1 M Potassium thiocyanate
Filter paper & funnel	Blender	Distilled Water
Cuvettes	Beaker tongs	100 grams Spinach Leaves
Pipette (± 0.05)	Thermometer (± 0.05)	

2.2 Variables

Table 1

Independent variable and method of temperature variation across trials

Independent Variable	Varied Values (°C)	How this will be varied
Temperature at which spinach was cooked	Room temperature 25, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80	Temperature will be maintained by use of a water bath

Table 2 Dependent variable and method of measurement

Dependent Variable	How this will be measured
Amount of Iron (III) in spinach which is directly proportional to the absorbance	After treatment of cooked spinach, at a specific temperature, with KSCN, absorbance would be found with a colorimeter set to a wavelength of 470 nm. Values of absorbance will be converted to exact concentration using a standard calibration curve.

Table 3

Controlled variables, methods of control, and their significance to the validity of the investigation

Controlled Variables	How this will be controlled	Significance
Volume of spinach mixture in each sample (13 mL) from the parent solution	Use a measuring cylinder to measure 13 mL of mixture for each sample	This was to ensure that each sample has the same amount of spinach which means the same amount of initial iron.
Mass of spinach and water used to make the mixture	Measured mass of spinach by use of an electric balance and measured the volume of volume water through a measuring cylinder.	The known amounts were blended to create a homogenous mixture, thus a consistent amount of iron in each sample.
Volume of HCl, nitric acid and KSCN solution added	Use a 10 mL pipette to measure each required amount of solution	Inconsistent measurement of chemicals added will affect the precision of the experiment
Time to cook each sample at a specific temperature	Timer used to place the sample beakers in the water bath for only 5 minutes	Keeping the cooking time constant ensures that the extent of iron release solely depends on the temperature, not the duration of exposure.

2.3 Procedure

Parts of this procedure, involving the preparation of the spinach and absorbance determination with the use of a spectrophotometer, was obtained from the University of Purdue (15). Colorimetric analysis was chosen over titration, in order to avoid challenges

like end point determination. It used 2.5 grams of food sample. This was doubled in my experiment to achieve higher absorbance readings and lower percent uncertainty. Furthermore, due to time and equipment restraints, the spinach was not ashed. Instead, a blended homogenous mixture was used, which allowed even distribution of iron. The challenges with making the mixture were faced; ample water had to be added in order to ensure smooth blending. Furthermore, the spinach stems were omitted from the sample as they contain less iron than the leaves. The selected temperature range is chosen to observe the gradual effect of increasing temperature; room temperature serves as a baseline while avoiding going higher than 80 °C which could degrade iron, as well as be difficult to achieve by laboratory water bath. The total final solution volume was assumed to be 26 mL; liquid retention during filtration was negligible as solid residue on filter paper was dry.

To determine the actual iron concentration of the spinach samples cooked at different temperatures, a standard calibration curve was obtained from a secondary source (16). The standard curve measured Fe^{3+} absorbance at 465 nm, which is quite close to the wavelength of the colorimeter. The linear equation from the calibration curve was used to convert experimental absorbance values into iron concentrations.

Making the spinach solution

In order to ensure that each sample taken from the spinach mixture contains 5g of spinach, correct proportions of spinach and water must be added.

If I use 100 g of spinach and 160 mL of water, the total mass of the mixture would be 260 g. (since 1 ml = 1g)

Fraction of the mixture that is spinach is:

$$(eq3) \quad \frac{\text{mass of spinach}}{\text{total mass of mixture}} = \frac{100}{260} \approx 0.3846$$

That means 38.46% of the mixture is spinach.

Mass of spinach per sample:

$$(eq4) \quad \frac{\text{desired mass of spinach}}{\text{spinach fraction}} = \frac{5}{0.3846} = 13.0 \text{ g}$$

Thus, for every sample, you need to measure 13 grams of mixture, which will contain approximately 5 grams of spinach.

Making KSCN solution

- Take 0.97g of KSCN powder and dissolve in 100 mL of distilled water. This makes a 0.1 M solution.

Boiling the spinach samples

1. Cut off the stems of the spinach leaves and weigh out 100 grams of spinach leaves using a measuring balance.
2. Add 160 mL of distilled water and the spinach leaves into a blender.
3. Blend the leaves and water in a laboratory blender until a homogeneous mixture is formed. Take 13 mL of the mixture into a beaker and place it in a water bath.
4. Cook the mixture in a water bath at the desired temperature of 40°C for exactly 5 minutes.
5. Dip in ice-cold water momentarily to stop the cooking.

Preparing the samples

6. Add 10 mL of 2.0 M HCl to the spinach beaker using a pipette. Stir carefully for one minute.
7. Filter the mixture; collect the filtrate in a beaker.
8. Add 0.5 mL of concentrated nitric acid, to ensure all iron is in Fe³⁺ ion.
9. Add 2.5 mL of 0.1 M KSCN to the solution using a pipette. Stir well. This will turn the solution red.

Finding Absorbance

10. Using a small dropper, each solution was transferred to a separate cuvette
11. Set the colorimeter at 470 nm. Use distilled water with KSCN and HCl as a blank for calibration.
12. Place the cuvette in the spectrophotometer and record the absorbance reading.
13. Repeat the steps 1-12 for each cooking temperature (50°C, 60°C, 70°C and 80°C) and hold 3 trials to ensure accuracy.

2.4 Precautions

Table 5

Safety precautions taken during the investigation and their associated hazards

Safety Precautions	Significance
Wash hands thoroughly after handling HCl	Harmful if swallowed, inhaled or in contact with skin (17)
Use fume hood while using nitric acid and HCl	May cause respiratory irritation (17)

Wear safety goggles and gloves	Protection against any accidental spillage
Do not leave water bath unattended	Risk of fire
Avoid breathing KSCN dust and avoid eye and skin contact	Can cause acute toxicity (18)

Environmental and Ethical Precautions

Wastage of food could be considered unethical, but has been done for scientific purposes in this case. The waste was reduced by using a minimum mass of spinach required. Chemicals could not be disposed of into a sink. After using electrical items, they were switched off immediately.

3. Results

3.1 Raw Data

Table 6

Qualitative colour observations of the spinach extract at each cooking temperature.

Temperature °C / ±0.1	uncooked	40.0	50.0	60.0	70.0	80.0
Qualitative Observations	dirty green	orange	orange	Orange green	Deep orange	Deep orange

Table 7

Raw absorbance values for three trials at each cooking temperature, measured at 470 nm

Cooking Temperature (±0.1 °C)	Trial	Absorbance (±0.001)
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Room temperature	1	0.812
	2	1.168
	3	0.322
40.0	1	0.599
	2	0.503
	3	0.577
50.0	1	0.649
	2	0.611
	3	0.625
60.0	1	0.650
	2	0.661
	3	0.655
70.0	1	0.677
	2	0.654
	3	0.638
80.0	1	0.767
	2	0.700
	3	0.647

3.2 Statistical Analysis

The absorbance values of the three trials were averaged to find the average absorbance of iron in 5 grams of spinach boiled at different temperatures.

$$(eq5) \quad \text{Mean absorbance} = \frac{(\text{trial 1} + \text{trial 2} + \text{trial 3})}{3}$$

For example, at the temperature of 40°C:

$$= \frac{0.599 + 0.503 + 0.577}{3}$$

$$= 0.5597 \approx 0.560$$

Trials of room temperature/uncooked were not included since its trials did not match despite being repeated 4 times. Spread uncertainty was also calculated and displayed as

error bars on the graph. This is to account for variability in measurements for multiple trials.

$$(eq6) \quad \text{Spread Uncertainty} = \frac{\text{max}-\text{min}}{2}$$

For example, at 80 °C:

$$\frac{0.767 - 0.647}{2} = 0.060$$

Table 8

Mean absorbance, standard deviation, standard error, 95% confidence interval, and coefficient of variation of triplicate absorbance measurements at each cooking temperature

Temperature (°C)	Mean Absorbance (±0.001)	Standard Deviation	Spread Uncertainty	Coefficient of Variation (%)	Standard Error	95% Confidence Interval
40.0	0.560	0.0503	0.048	8.98	0.0290	±0.125
50.0	0.628	0.0192	0.019	3.06	0.0111	±0.048
60.0	0.655	0.0055	0.006	0.84	0.0032	±0.014
70.0	0.656	0.0196	0.020	2.99	0.0113	±0.049
80.0	0.705	0.0601	0.060	8.52	0.0347	±0.149

$$(eq7) \quad \text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

where n=3, \bar{x} is your average absorbance, and x^i are the three trial values

For example, at 80 °C:

$$(0.705 - 0.767)^2 = 0.003844$$

$$(0.705 - 0.700)^2 = 0.000025$$

$$(0.705 - 0.647)^2 = 0.003364$$

$$\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 = 0.003844 + 0.000025 + 0.003364 = 0.007233$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{0.007233}{2}} = 0.0601$$

$$CV = \frac{SD}{Mean} \times 100$$

for example, at 80 °C:

$$\frac{0.0601}{0.705} = 0.0852 = 8.52\%$$

$$(eq8) \quad Standard\ Error = \frac{standard\ deviation}{\sqrt{n}} = \frac{standard\ deviation}{\sqrt{3}}$$

for example, at 80 °C:

$$SE = \frac{0.0601}{\sqrt{3}} = 0.0347$$

With n=3 trials per temperature, the degrees of freedom (df = n-1) equal 2. For a 95% confidence level at df=2, the corresponding two-tailed critical t-value, obtained from a standard t-distribution table, is 4.303 (19). This t-value was used to calculate the 95% confidence interval for each temperature

$$(eq9) \quad 95\% CI = \pm(t \times SE)$$

where t=4.303 for n=3, degrees of freedom=2 at 95% confidence level

for example, at 80 °C:

$$4.303 \times 0.0347 = 0.149$$

$$95\% CI = 0.705 \pm 0.149 = [0.556, 0.854]$$

Pearson Correlation and Significance Test

Table 9

Deviations of temperature and absorbance from their respective means, used in the calculation of the Pearson correlation coefficient

Temperature (x)	Absorbance (y)	$x - \underline{x}$	$y - \underline{y}$	$(x - \underline{x})(y - \underline{y})$	$(x - \underline{x})^2$	$(y - \underline{y})^2$
40.0	0.560	-20	-0.081	1.620	400	0.006561
50.0	0.628	-10	-0.013	0.130	100	0.000169
60.0	0.655	0	0.014	0.000	0	0.000196
70.0	0.656	10	0.015	0.150	100	0.000225
80.0	0.705	20	0.064	1.280	400	0.004096

$$(eq10) \quad \text{Pearson } R \text{ formula} = \frac{\Sigma(x-\underline{x})(y-\underline{y})}{\sqrt{\Sigma(x-\underline{x})^2 \times \Sigma(y-\underline{y})^2}}$$

where x is temperature, y is absorbance, \underline{x} and \underline{y} are their respective means

$$\underline{x} = \frac{40 + 50 + 60 + 70 + 80}{5} = 60$$

$$\underline{y} = \frac{0.560 + 0.628 + 0.655 + 0.656 + 0.705}{5} = 0.641$$

$$\Sigma(x - \underline{x})(y - \underline{y}) = 3.18$$

$$\Sigma(x - \underline{x})^2 = 1000$$

$$\Sigma(y - \underline{y})^2 = 0.011247$$

$$R = \frac{3.180}{\sqrt{1000 \times 0.011247}} = 0.948$$

$$(eq11) \quad t = R \times \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{(1-R^2)}}$$

where n(number of data points)=5, R=0.948

$$t = 0.948 \times \sqrt{\frac{5-2}{(1-(0.948)^2)}} = 5.159$$

For n=5 data points, degrees of freedom for the correlation significance test equal n-2=3. The critical t-value at df=3 for a two-tailed test at $\alpha=0.05$ (95% confidence) is 3.182 (19). Since $5.16 > 3.182$, the calculated value exceeds the critical threshold.

Comparison of Absorbance Values at 60°C and 70°C

Mean absorbance at 60°C = 0.655 SD at 60°C = 0.0055

Mean absorbance at 70°C = 0.656 SD at 70°C = 0.0196

$$Difference = 0.656 - 0.655 = 0.001$$

The calculated difference (0.001) is equal to the instrument resolution (± 0.001) and smaller than the standard deviation at both temperatures.

Error Propagation

Uncertainty in spinach mixture:

$$\text{Analytical Balance: } \frac{0.001}{100} \times 100 = 0.001 \%$$

$$\text{Pipette: } \frac{0.05}{160} \times 100 = 0.0313\%$$

Uncertainty in colorimeter:

$$\frac{0.001}{0.738} \times 100 = 0.136\%$$

Uncertainty in temperature:

$$\frac{0.05}{80} \times 100 = 0.0625\%$$

Total Uncertainty:

$$= (0.001 + 0.0313 + 0.136 + 0.0625)\%$$

$$= 0.231 \%$$

$$= 0.738 \times 0.231 \%$$

$$= 0.738 \pm 0.0017$$

3.3 Concentration and Iron Content Calculations

Figure 3. Standard calibration curve for Fe³⁺ concentration (μg/mL) versus absorbance, used to convert experimental absorbance values to Fe³⁺ concentration (16)

Using the equation,

$$(eq12) \quad C = \frac{Abs - 0.0085}{0.0353}$$

For example, at 80 °C:

$$C = \frac{0.705 - 0.0085}{0.0353} = 19.731$$

Table 10

Fe³⁺ concentration in the final solution, calculated from absorbance using the calibration curve (16)

Temperature (°C)	Average Absorbance	Fe ³⁺ Concentration (µg/mL)
40.0	0.560	15.6
50.0	0.628	17.5
60.0	0.655	18.3
70.0	0.656	18.3
80.0	0.705	19.7

Table 11

Estimated iron content per 100 g of spinach at each cooking temperature, calculated from final solution concentration and sample mass

Temperature (°C)	Fe ³⁺ Concentration (µg/mL)	Total Fe ³⁺ (µg) in 26 mL	Per 5g spinach (µg/g)	mg/100g spinach
40.0	15.6	405.6	81.1	8.11
50.0	17.5	455	91.0	9.10
60.0	18.3	475.8	95.2	9.52
70.0	18.3	475.8	95.2	9.52
80.0	19.7	512.2	102.4	10.24

The Fe³⁺ concentration in the final solution (µg/mL) was converted to iron content per 100g spinach using the total final solution volume of 26 mL and the known sample mass of 5g spinach per trial. This conversion was applied across all temperatures and results are presented in Table 4.

For example, at 80 °C:

$$\text{Total Fe}^{3+} = 19.7 \mu\text{g/mL} \times 26\text{mL} = 512.2\mu\text{g}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Iron content per 100g spinach} &= (512.2 \mu\text{g} \div 5\text{g}) \times 100 \\ &= 10,244 \mu\text{g}/100 \text{ g} = 10.24 \text{ mg}/100\text{g} \end{aligned}$$

Table 12

Percentage increase in mean absorbance between successive and extreme temperature intervals

Temperature Interval (°C)	Percentage Increase (%)
40 to 50	12.14
50 to 60	4.30
60 to 70	0.15
70 to 80	7.47
40 to 80	31.79

Example calculation:

$$(eq13) \quad \text{Percentage Increase} = \frac{\text{New Value} - \text{Old Value}}{\text{Old value}} \times 100$$

Absorbance at 40 °C = 0.560

Absorbance at 80°C = 0.738

$$= \frac{0.738 - 0.560}{0.560}$$

$$\frac{0.178}{0.560} \times 100 = 31.79$$

3.4 Graphical Representation

Figure 4. Mean absorbance of the Fe^{3+} -thiocyanate complex plotted against spinach cooking temperature (40-80°C), with error bars representing standard deviation across three trials at each temperature

Figure 5. Estimated Fe^{3+} concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) plotted against spinach cooking temperature (40-80°C), derived from the calibration curve shown in Figure 3

4. Discussion

4.1 Analysis

The mathematical relationship between spinach cooking temperature and average absorbance by iron content can be supported by the equation, $y = 0.003x + 0.45$, with $R^2 = 0.899$. It indicates that the model is a strong fit as it is pretty close to 1. Furthermore, it suggests that 89.9% of variation in absorbance is due to temperature changes. The gradient of the graph is 0.003 which means that for every 1°C in temperature, there is a

0.003 increase in absorbance. As for the depicted relationship between temperature and ΔC iron concentration, the gradient implies that $\frac{\Delta C}{\Delta T} = 0.09 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Furthermore, the y-intercept is significant for an extrapolated prediction. It means that if the model was extended to 0°C , the absorbance would be 0.45.

To verify the relationship between cooking temperature and average absorbance independently, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated directly from the raw temperature-absorbance data. The coefficient ($R=0.948$) matched the regression's R^2 , as $(0.948)^2 = 0.8987$, which confirms the regression analysis is internally consistent. This correlation was tested for statistical significance using a t-test, yielding $t=5.16$ ($df=3$). Since this exceeds the critical t-value of 3.182 at the 95% confidence level, the correlation is statistically significant ($p<0.05$). The t-test confirms that the correlation is not coincidental, supporting the hypothesis that higher temperatures release more iron. Between 60°C and 70°C , we see a saturation point as the concentration remains constant at $18.3 \mu\text{g/mL}$. The difference in mean absorbance between 60°C and 70°C ($\Delta=0.001$) is equal to the stated instrument resolution of the colorimeter (± 0.001), and smaller than the standard deviation at either temperature ($SD_{60}=0.0055$, $SD_{70}=0.0196$). This indicates that the apparent plateau in iron release between these two temperatures reflects a statistically negligible difference rather than a meaningful increase. This statistical confirmation is consistent with the percentage increase data, which shows 31.79% rise from $40\text{--}80^\circ\text{C}$, only 0.15% between $60\text{--}70^\circ\text{C}$, 12.14% between $40\text{--}50^\circ\text{C}$.

However, the experimental absorbance values at room temperature (0.812, 1.168, 0.322) show discrepancies and do not follow the general trend, relative to other temperature sets. Their values showed substantial internal inconsistency across replicate trials. This inconsistency can be justified by the oxalate binding of iron. At lower temperatures, oxalates remain bonded to iron. Thus, the high presence of ferrous oxalates makes iron unavailable and leads to incomplete extraction. The variation suggests that iron was not available in these trials, due to almost negligible breakdown of iron-oxalate complexes. This resulted in an incomplete reaction of iron with potassium thiocyanate. This is supported by the qualitative observation of no orange colour change in the solution. The variation in these trials shows the challenges that may be faced if iron content is explored at lower temperatures.

The estimated iron content across the tested temperature range (8.11–10.24 mg/100g spinach) exceeds typical literature-reported values for raw or boiled spinach (approximately 2.7–3.6 mg/100g) (20). This discrepancy is attributable to the acidic extraction conditions used in this study (HCl and nitric acid treatment), which liberate iron beyond what is naturally bioavailable through digestion alone.

4.2 Evaluation

While the statistical analysis supports a genuine relationship between cooking temperature and iron release, several methodological limitations affect the precision and generalisability of these findings. The use of a blended, non-ashed spinach mixture, while necessary given equipment constraints, introduces potential variability in sample homogeneity between trials. Slight variation could impact iron concentration across samples. It means small differences in blending could have contributed to the resulting conclusion within repeated replicate trials, independent of the temperature effect itself. This variation could be handled by a slight change in methodology; spinach leaves could be ashed like the procedure of the University of Purdue (15), which could not be done in this study due to time and equipment constraints. A more significant limitation is the potential for evaporation during the five-minute heating period, particularly at higher temperatures. Water loss in an open beaker would concentrate the remaining solution, meaning a portion of the apparent increase in absorbance at higher temperatures may reflect concentration effects rather than true iron release alone.

Also, the intensity of the $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})^{3+}$ complex is known to be pH-dependent, and although acid volumes were held constant across samples, pH itself was not directly measured or controlled. This represents a source of uncertainty not captured in the stated error propagation. The use of 1,10-phenanthroline is more appropriate as it forms a more stable compound which is less susceptible to pH change.

It should be noted that the calibration curve used to convert absorbance to Fe^{3+} concentration was derived using a different reagent and a slightly different wavelength (465 nm) than the KSCN-based methodology at 470 nm used in this study. This introduces systematic uncertainty into the absolute concentration values reported, though the relative trend across temperatures remains valid since the same calibration curve was used consistently to all samples.

Collectively, these limitations suggest that while the statistical significance of the temperature-absorbance relationship is robust, the absolute concentration values reported should be interpreted with appropriate caution.

4.3 Extension

A further experiment could investigate the effect of different cooking methods, such as steaming or microwaving, to determine if temperature changes impact the iron content in a similar way to boiling. This direction is supported by existing literature, such as Masrizal et al. (21), found that iron retention is significantly higher when cooked by microwave-steaming compared to boiling, suggesting that cooking method itself, independent of temperature, may meaningfully affect iron retention and therefore, supports further investigation alongside the temperature variable explored in this study. Additionally, examining the effect of cooking duration could help identify the optimal cooking time to preserve the iron content in spinach. Expanding the investigation to

include different types of spinach, such as baby spinach or mature spinach, would provide insights into whether variations in type influence the iron concentration. These extensions would broaden the scope of the study and provide more comprehensive conclusions about iron retention in spinach.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this investigation was to determine the amount of iron in spinach after cooking at different temperatures for a constant time. Through colorimetric analysis, the results of the experiment support the hypothesis and demonstrate a positive correlation between temperature and average absorbance through the mathematical model. The statistical test of a positive and very close to +1 'R-value' implies a strong correlation between the variables. This was tested for significance ($t=5.16 > \text{critical } 3.182, p<0.05$) which confirms that the relationship is not due to chance. The qualitative observations also show a deepening of red colour, thus more ironthiocyanate complexes in the solution. As for the obtained iron concentrations at different temperatures, the trend supports the hypothesis that measurable iron content increases as temperature increases. The low percentage and absolute uncertainties further strengthen the accuracy of the findings, thereby supporting the drawn conclusion. These findings align with established theories on oxalate-iron binding; higher cooking temperatures facilitate the breakdown of oxalate-iron complexes in spinach, thereby increasing the amount of iron detected in solution. The estimated iron content across the tested temperature range (8.11–10.24 mg/100g spinach) exceeds typical literature-reported values for raw or boiled spinach (approximately 2.7–3.6 mg/100g) (20). Extractable Fe^{3+} content increased with temperature under the acidic laboratory conditions used in this study, which reflects extraction efficiency. Therefore, the conclusion can be drawn that cooking temperature has a statistically significant, measurable effect on the extractable iron content of spinach, with implications for optimizing extraction methods in food science applications. While these findings are statistically robust, the use of a secondary calibration curve and the acidic extraction method mean absolute concentration values should be interpreted with appropriate caution. Future work using an in-house calibration curve could refine these estimates.

6. References

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